

Plant Biodiversity in the Urban-Rural Gradient of the Uruguay-Brazil Binational Border

Traversa, Ignacio <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8490-7966>

Nolla, Sarita <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-7740-6057>

Mallo, Agustín <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-5175-0861>

Abstract

This study analyzed changes in woody flora biodiversity along the urban-rural gradient in the border cities of Rivera (Uruguay) and Livramento (Brazil). The methodology consisted of surveying 50 circular plots of 20 m radius, divided into five concentric strata up to 7.5 km from the International Park. Floristic composition, abundance, and origin (native or introduced) of 1,379 woody flora individuals were assessed. Results identified 126 species, with an almost equal balance between native (62) and introduced (64) species. The most abundant families were Myrtaceae, Anacardiaceae, and Fabaceae. Simple regression analysis showed a strong and positive linear relationship between the Natural Biodiversity Index (NB') and Distance to the Urban Center (DC) ($R^2 = 0.629$), indicating that the proportion of native species significantly increases further from the urban core. A positive relationship was also found with the locally available Natural Area (NA) ($R^2 = 0.242$). The multiple linear regression model (DC and Construction-Free Area Quotient, (C)) was statistically significant (R^2 adjusted = 0.355), confirming that distance to urbanization and local habitat quality are key, independent predictors of native biodiversity. The findings confirm the negative effect of urbanization on native flora in central areas and emphasize the need to integrate native forest conservation with cross-border territorial management policies.

Keywords: Natural Biodiversity Index (NB'); Woody flora; Invasive species; Native forest

1. Introduction

The relationship between native and exotic species in urban and rural environments has been a subject of sustained scientific debate, particularly regarding its effects on biodiversity. Traditionally, the so-called "invasion paradigm" posited that exotic species displace native ones, thereby reducing local diversity. However, recent research has evidenced greater ecological complexity. In particular, a global meta-analysis found a positive correlation between native and exotic species richness across different spatial scales, indicating that more diverse habitats can simultaneously harbor a higher number of both (Peng et al., 2019).

Nevertheless, these effects are neither uniform nor linear. In restored prairies, for instance, exotic species have been identified as the primary factor reducing plant diversity due to their high competitive capacity for resources (Kaul & Wilsey, 2021). A paradigmatic case is *Ligustrum lucidum*, an exotic species widely introduced for ornamental purposes (Resende Araújo et al., 2022), whose phenotypic plasticity has allowed it to become a dominant structural invader in diverse ecosystems (Fernández et al., 2020), with long-term negative impacts on local biodiversity (Bowler, Bjorkman & Hines, 2022).

Conversely, mature native trees have proven to act as effective biotic barriers, inhibiting the establishment of exotic species by competing for light, water, and nutrients (Rossignaud et al., 2022). This type of interaction is profoundly altered by urbanization processes, which modify floristic diversity patterns and promote the replacement of specialist species with generalist ones (Aronson et al., 2014; Vakhlamova et al., 2014). Indeed, in Latin American

cities such as Portoviejo (Ecuador), it has been observed that rural ecosystems—being less fragmented—retain greater species richness and ecological resilience capacity compared to urban ones (Pacheco Cobeña & Guerrero Calero, 2024; McKinney, 2008).

Rural areas, by maintaining a less disturbed ecological structure, function as floristic reservoirs with a higher capacity to respond to disturbances (Seto et al., 2012). Nonetheless, even in protected areas such as the Rivera and Livramento International Park (Brazil-Uruguay), a worrying predominance of exotic species over native ones is recorded (Araujo et al., 2012), reflecting constant pressure on regional biodiversity.

Uruguay constitutes an especially relevant case due to its location in a phytogeographical transition zone between the subtropical and Pampean provinces. This condition favors a remarkable woody richness, composed of native species of high ecological and economic value (Haretche, Mai & Brazeiro, 2012). However, invasion processes such as the one led by *Ligustrum lucidum*, which establishes itself with particular success in forest edges and disturbed areas, threaten to erode this diversity (García, Cabaña & Perdomo, 2024). In this regard, the conservation of native forests cannot be addressed in isolation; rather, it must be articulated with territorial management policies, integrating in situ conservation with landscape approaches (Heywood & Iriondo, 2003).

Furthermore, it is necessary to revalue the bioeconomic potential of native flora as a sustainable development strategy, as proposed by Bennadji et al. (2014) through bioprospecting and the comprehensive utilization of native species such as *Eugenia uniflora* or *Allophylus edulis* (Cárdenas & Vásquez, 2021). Tools such as the IIAL (Integrated Index of Anthropization Landscape / INRA) allow the identification of the degree of human intervention in the landscape, guiding decision-making in conservation matters (Martínez-Dueñas, 2010).

Detailed floristic knowledge is also fundamental. Studies on the coastal vegetation of southeastern Uruguay have allowed the characterization of unique environments that require protection (Alonso Paz & Bassagoda, 2002), while recent research highlights the importance of native floral resources for pollinators and the maintenance of key ecosystem functions (Díaz et al., 2021).

It is worth noting that not all exotic species constitute a threat: many of them fail to establish viable populations without human intervention (Capdevila-Argüelles, Zilletti & Suárez Álvarez, 2005). However, when they succeed, they can generate significant impacts on biodiversity, the economy, and health, becoming one of the primary causes of biological diversity loss on a global scale (Sanz et al., 2018).

In this context, the objective of the present study is to analyze the changes in plant biodiversity along the urban-rural gradient in the border cities of Rivera (Uruguay) and Livramento (Brazil), evaluating floristic composition, the presence of exotic and invasive species, and the ecological implications for native forest conservation in a transboundary environment.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study Area

The study was conducted within an urban area with a 7.5-kilometer radius, centered at the International Park of Rivera (Uruguay) and Sant'Ana do Livramento (Brazil). This area constitutes a binational border zone where both cities function as a single conurbation or urban core.

From a demographic perspective, this binational core consolidates a population exceeding 180,000 inhabitants. Specifically, the city of Rivera has a population of 103,493 inhabitants according to the National Institute of Statistics of Uruguay, while Sant'Ana do Livramento records 84,421 inhabitants according to the Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística. The estimated average population density in the built-up area is approximately 220 inhabitants/ha, demonstrating a consolidated urban fabric with high anthropic interaction.

Regarding climate, the region is classified under the Köppen-Geiger system as Cfa (humid subtropical climate), characterized by the absence of a well-defined dry season and hot summers. The average annual temperature is around 18°C, with fluctuations ranging from an average of 12°C in the winter months to 24°C during the summer period. Rainfall is abundant and evenly distributed throughout the year, with annual cumulative precipitation of 1400 mm, which favors both the development of native vegetation and the adaptation of introduced species.

The study area was divided into five concentric strata extending from the aforementioned center: Stratum I (0–1,500 m from the center), Stratum II (1,501–3,000 m), Stratum III (3,001–4,500 m), Stratum IV (4,501–6,000 m), and Stratum V (6,001–7,500 m). Within each stratum, 10 randomized sampling plots were established, divided equally with five plots for each of the two cities, totaling 50 plots. Each plot consisted of a circular area with a 20-meter radius, covering a surface area of 1257 m².

2.2. Data Collection

For field data collection, satellite imagery of the urban core was utilized to delineate polygons with green areas exceeding 6,400 m². These polygons were selected through random drawing. Subsequently, during fieldwork, a central point was randomly selected within each polygon to serve as the plot center. From this point, a 20 m radius was established to define a circular sampling plot, within which a complete census of all woody flora species present was conducted.

Geographic coordinates of the plot center and its distance to the urban origin (International Park) were recorded. The surveyed woody flora was defined as the assemblage of shrubs and trees with a height equal to or greater than two meters. Additionally, individual abundance per species and the geographic origin of the recorded species were documented. Species were classified as native if they grow naturally within a 300 km radius in the region, and as introduced if their origin exceeded this radius.

2.3. Data Processing

Field data were organized into a Microsoft Excel matrix containing information for each plot. The grouping variables included: city, stratum, geographic coordinates, distance to

the urbanization center, botanical order, botanical family, scientific name, species origin, species abundance, and relative frequency by family and species (Araujo, 2012).

Given that the study area is a disturbed region featuring non-native species, a specific biodiversity index was required to evaluate the probability [0-1] that two randomly selected individuals belong to different species, under the condition that these species are simultaneously native. To achieve this, the Natural Biodiversity Index (BN') (Traversa, 2024) (equation 1):

$$NB' = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{n_i \cdot n_{ic}}{N \cdot N - 1} \quad (1)$$

where:

n_i : total number of individuals of the native species i ,

n_{ic} : total number of individuals of the complement of the native species i (i.e., the total number of individuals of all other native species present),

N : total number of individuals of all species (both native and introduced) present in the plot.

In parallel, Google Earth software was used to calculate the built-up area surrounding each of the 50 plots. For this purpose, a 100 m radius was mapped around each plot on the satellite image, delimiting an area equivalent to 31,416 m². Within each circle, polygons representing the built-up area were digitized. Built-up area was defined as structures (buildings, houses, sheds) and communication routes (streets, roads, paths, and highways).

The natural area (NA) was obtained by subtracting the built-up area (CA) from the total area (TA). To normalize this variable within the [0-1] space, the ratio between the natural area and the total area was applied.

Finally, a regression analysis was performed to model the natural biodiversity index of each plot as a function of its distance to the urban center of origin (DC). Furthermore, the function linking the natural area (NA , defined as the construction-free area) of each plot with the natural biodiversity index (BN') was analyzed, followed by a multiple linear regression analysis predicting BN' from DC and CA .

3. Results

A total of 126 species belonging to 46 botanical families were identified. The number of native species was 62, while introduced species accounted for 64 species. The total number of surveyed individuals was 1,379, which implies a density of 219 individuals per hectare (Table 1).

Table 1. List of identified species by family, origin (I = introduced; N = native), abundance, and relative frequency in percentage.

Familia	Nombre Científico	Origen	Abundancia	Frecuencia relativa (%)
Altingiaceae	<i>Liquidambar styraciflua</i> L.	I	4	0,290
Anacardiaceae	<i>Lithraea brasiliensis</i> Marchand	N	96	6,962
	<i>Mangifera indica</i> Wall.	I	2	0,145
	<i>Schinus lentiscifolius</i> f. <i>flexuosus</i> Chodat & Hassl	N	21	1,523
	<i>Schinus longifolius</i> (Lindl.) Speg.	N	24	1,740

Traversa, I., Nolla, S., & Mallo, A. [2026]. Plant biodiversity in the urban-rural gradient of the Uruguay-Brazil binational border. v2. 13 p. Zenodo. [10.5281/zenodo.20401780].

	<i>Schinus molle</i> L.	N	17	1,233
	<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i> Raddi	N	9	0,653
Aquifoliaceae	<i>Ilex dumosa</i> Reissek	N	2	0,145
Araliaceae	<i>Schefflera arboricola</i> Hayata	I	3	0,218
Araucariaceae	<i>Araucaria heterophylla</i> (Salisb.) Franco,	I	2	0,145
Arecaceae	<i>Archontophoenix cunninghamiana</i> (H.Wendl.)	I	15	1,088
	<i>Butia capitata</i> (Mart.) Becc.	N	2	0,145
	<i>Phoenix canariensis</i> Nabonnand	I	16	1,160
	<i>Syagrus romanzoffiana</i> (Cham.) Glassman	N	9	0,653
	<i>Washingtonia robusta</i> H.Wendl.	I	2	0,145
Asparagaceae	<i>Cordyline australis</i> (G. Forst.) Endl.	I	1	0,073
Asteraceae	<i>Acanthostyles buniifolium</i> (Hook. y Arn.)	N	17	1,233
	<i>Austroeupeatorium inulifolium</i> (Kunth) R.M.King & H.Rob	N	1	0,073
	<i>Baccharis dracunculifolia</i> DC.	N	24	1,740
	<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i> L.	N	3	0,218
	<i>Baccharis punctulata</i> DC.	N	4	0,290
	<i>Radlkoferotoma berroi</i> (Hutch.) RM King & H.Rob.	N	1	0,073
Bignoniaceae	<i>Jacaranda mimosifolia</i> D.Don	I	29	2,103
	<i>Tabebuia lapacho</i> (K.Schum.) Sandwith	N	4	0,290
Buxaceae	<i>Buxus balearica</i> Lam.	I	1	0,073
	<i>Buxus sempervirens</i> L.	I	1	0,073
	<i>Cereus hildmannianus</i> subsp. <i>uruguayanus</i> (F.Ritter ex R.Kiesling)			
Cactaceae	N.P.Taylor	N	1	0,073
Cannabaceae	<i>Celtis tala</i> Gillies ex Planch.	N	1	0,073
Casuarinaceae	<i>Casuarina cunninghamiana</i> Miq.	I	1	0,073
Celastraceae	<i>Maytenus ilicifolia</i> (Schrad.) Planch.	N	10	0,725
Cupressaceae	<i>Cupressus arizonica</i> Greene	I	16	1,160
	<i>Cupressus lusitanica</i> Mill.	I	2	0,145
	<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i> L.	I	13	0,943
	<i>Platycladus orientalis</i> (L.) Franco	I	2	0,145
	<i>Thuja occidentalis</i> L.	I	4	0,290
Cycadaceae	<i>Cycas revoluta</i> Bedd.	I	1	0,073
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Croton urucurana</i> Baill.	N	1	0,073
	<i>Manihot grahamii</i> Hook.	N	1	0,073
	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	I	5	0,363
	<i>Sebastiania commersoniana</i> (Baill.) L.B.Sm. & Downs	N	2	0,145
Fabaceae	<i>Bauhinia forficata</i> , Enum. Hort. Berol.	N	4	0,290
	<i>Calliandra tweediei</i> Benth.	N	6	0,435
	<i>Enterolobium contortisiliquum</i> (Vell.) Morong	N	11	0,798
	<i>Erythrina crista-galli</i> L.	N	17	1,233
	<i>Gleditsia triacanthos</i> L.	I	3	0,218
	<i>Inga uraguensis</i> Hook. & Arn.	N	7	0,508
	<i>Mimosa bimucronata</i> (DC.) Kuntze	N	1	0,073
	<i>Mimosa pudica</i> L.	N	16	1,160
	<i>Parapiptadenia rigida</i> (Benth.) Brenan	N	18	1,305
	<i>Peltophorum dubium</i> (Spreng.) Taub.	N	5	0,363
	<i>Quercus bicolor</i> Willd.	I	1	0,073
	<i>Quercus robur</i> L.	I	1	0,073
	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> L.	I	2	0,145
	<i>Sesbania virgata</i> (Cav.) Poir.	N	1	0,073
	<i>Tipuana tipu</i> (Benth.) Kuntze	I	1	0,073
	<i>Vachellia caven</i> (Molina) Seigler & Ebinger	N	64	4,641
Lauraceae	<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i> (Fabr.)	I	1	0,073
	<i>Nectandra angustifolia</i> (Schrad.) Nees & Mart.	N	10	0,725
	<i>Ocotea acutifolia</i> (Nees) Mez	N	26	1,885
	<i>Ocotea pulchella</i> Mart.	N	2	0,145
	<i>Persea americana</i> Mill.	I	6	0,435
Magnoliaceae	<i>Magnolia grandiflora</i> L.	I	2	0,145
Malvaceae	<i>Brachychiton populneus</i> R.Br.	I	2	0,145
	<i>Chorisia speciosa</i> A.St.-Hil., A.Juss. & Cambess.	I	3	0,218
	<i>Hibiscus syriacus</i> L.	I	4	0,290
	<i>Luehea divaricata</i> Mart.	N	15	1,088
Meliaceae	<i>Ekebergia capensis</i> Sparrm	I	3	0,218
	<i>Melia azedarach</i> L.	I	6	0,435
Moraceae	<i>Ficus carica</i> L.	I	2	0,145

Traversa, I., Nolla, S., & Mallo, A. [2026]. Plant biodiversity in the urban-rural gradient of the Uruguay-Brazil binational border. v2. 13 p. Zenodo. [10.5281/zenodo.20401780].

	<i>Ficus elastica</i> Roxb.	I	2	0,145
	<i>Morus alba</i> L.	I	2	0,145
	<i>Morus nigra</i> L.	I	4	0,290
Primulaceae	<i>Myrsine laetevirens</i> (Mez) Arechav.	N	13	0,943
	<i>Rapanea ferruginea</i> (Ruiz & Pav.) Mez	N	5	0,363
Myrtaceae	<i>Acca sellowiana</i> (O.Berg) Burret, Repert	I	2	0,145
	<i>Blepharocalyx salicifolius</i> (Kunth) O. Berg	N	27	1,958
	<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> Dehnh.	I	89	6,454
	<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> Labill.	I	5	0,363
	<i>Eucalyptus robusta</i> Sm.	I	10	0,725
	<i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i> Sm.	I	84	6,091
	<i>Eugenia uniflora</i> L.	N	102	7,397
	<i>Myrceugenia glaucescens</i> (Cambess. ex A.St.-Hil.)	N	1	0,073
	<i>Myrcianthes pungens</i> (O.Berg) D.Legrand	N	4	0,290
	<i>Myrrhinium atropurpureum</i> Schott	N	9	0,653
	<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	I	7	0,508
Oleaceae	<i>Ligustrum lucidum</i> WTAiton	I	5	0,363
	<i>Ligustrum sinense</i> Lour.	I	19	1,378
	<i>Olea europaea</i> L.	I	1	0,073
Phytolaccaceae	<i>Phytolacca dioica</i> L.	N	1	0,073
Pinaceae	<i>Pinus elliottii</i> Engelm.	I	29	2,103
	<i>Pinus nigra</i> Aiton	I	1	0,073
	<i>Pinus patula</i> Schlttdl. & Cham.	I	1	0,073
	<i>Pinus taeda</i> L.	I	8	0,580
Platanaceae	<i>Platanus × acerifolia</i> (Aiton) Willd	I	8	0,580
Poaceae	<i>Bambusa tuldoidea</i> Munro	I	1	0,073
Proteaceae	<i>Grevillea robusta</i> A. Cunn. ex R.Br.	I	13	0,943
Quillajaceae	<i>Quillaja brasiliensis</i> Mart.	N	7	0,508
Rhamnaceae	<i>Hovenia dulcis</i> Thunb.	I	1	0,073
	<i>Scutia buxifolia</i> Reissek	N	26	1,885
Rosaceae	<i>Amygdalus persica</i> L.	I	5	0,363
	<i>Eriobotrya japonica</i> (Thunb.) Lindl.	I	3	0,218
	<i>Prunus sphaerocarpa</i> Sw.	N	3	0,218
	<i>Prunus subcoriacea</i> Koehne	N	14	1,015
	<i>Pyrus communis</i> L.	I	1	0,073
Rutaceae	<i>Citrus reticulata</i> Blanco	I	3	0,218
	<i>Citrus sinensis</i> Pers.	I	9	0,653
	<i>Zanthoxylum rhoifolium</i> Lam.	N	21	1,523
Salicaceae	<i>Casearia sylvestris</i> Sw.	N	15	1,088
	<i>Populus alba</i> L.	I	2	0,145
	<i>Salix babylonica</i> L.	I	2	0,145
	<i>Salix humboldtiana</i> Willd.	N	18	1,305
	<i>Xylosma tweediana</i> (Clos) Eichlam	N	3	0,218
Sapindaceae	<i>Allophylus edulis</i> Niederl.	N	54	3,916
	<i>Cupania vernalis</i> Cambess.	N	17	1,233
	<i>Matayba elaeagnoides</i> Radlk.	N	15	1,088
Scrophulariaceae	<i>Buddleja angusticarpa</i> (EMNorman & LBSm.) GPCoelho & Miotto	N	13	0,943
Solanaceae	<i>Nicotiana glauca</i> Graham	I	5	0,363
	<i>Solanum bonariense</i> L.	N	4	0,290
	<i>Solanum mauritanum</i> Scop.	N	10	0,725
Styracaceae	<i>Styrax leprosus f. latifolius</i> Chodat & Hassl.	N	13	0,943
Taxaceae	<i>Taxus baccata</i> L.	I	1	0,073
Taxodiaceae	<i>Taxodium distichum</i> (L.) Rich.	I	3	0,218
Theaceae	<i>Camellia japonica</i> L.	I	4	0,290
Thymelaeaceae	<i>Daphnopsis racemosa</i> Griseb.	N	6	0,435
Verbenaceae	<i>Aloysia gratissima</i> (Gillies & Hook.) Tronc.	N	37	2,683
	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	N	1	0,073
Total			1379	100

The most common botanical families were Myrtaceae (accounting for one-fourth of the total), Anacardiaceae (one-eighth), and Fabaceae (one-tenth). These data are partially consistent with Traversa and Alejano (2013), who reported that the Anacardiaceae family is the most abundant in rural areas, representing nearly 25% of the individuals (Table 2).

Traversa, I., Nolla, S., & Mallo, A. [2026]. Plant biodiversity in the urban-rural gradient of the Uruguay-Brazil binational border. v2. 13 p. Zenodo. [10.5281/zenodo.20401780].

Table 2. List of identified species by family, abundance, and relative frequency.

Family	Abundance	Relative Frequency (%)
Myrtaceae	340	24,656
Anacardiaceae	169	12,255
Fabaceae	158	11,458
Sapindaceae	86	6,236
Asteraceae	50	3,626
Lauraceae	45	3,263
Arecaceae	44	3,191
Salicaceae	40	2,901
Pinaceae	39	2,828
Verbenaceae	38	2,756
Cupressaceae	37	2,683
Bignoniaceae	33	2,393
Rutaceae	33	2,393
Rhamnaceae	27	1,958
Rosaceae	26	1,885
Oleaceae	25	1,813
Malvaceae	24	1,740
Solanaceae	19	1,378
Primulaceae	18	1,305
Proteaceae	13	0,943
Scrophulariaceae	13	0,943
Styracaceae	13	0,943
Celastraceae	10	0,725
Moraceae	10	0,725
Euphorbiaceae	9	0,653
Meliaceae	9	0,653
Platanaceae	8	0,580
Quillajaceae	7	0,508
Thymelaeaceae	6	0,435
Theaceae	4	0,290
Altingiaceae	4	0,290
Araliaceae	3	0,218
Taxodiaceae	3	0,218
Aquifoliaceae	2	0,145
Araucariaceae	2	0,145
Buxaceae	2	0,145
Magnoliaceae	2	0,145
Asparagaceae	1	0,073
Cactaceae	1	0,073
Cannabaceae	1	0,073
Casuarinaceae	1	0,073
Cycadaceae	1	0,073
Phytolaccaceae	1	0,073
Poaceae	1	0,073
Taxaceae	1	0,073

Although Myrtaceae is the most abundant family, it accounts for 102 individuals of *Eugenia uniflora* (a native species); nevertheless, there are 173 individuals belonging to the genus *Eucalyptus* (introduced species), whose cultivation is highly promoted, particularly on the Uruguayan side of the study region. Within the Anacardiaceae family, the most common species is *Lithraea brasiliensis* with 96 individuals. The Fabaceae family presented the highest species richness, with a record of 16 species.

The regression analysis between natural biodiversity (BN') and the distance to the urban center shows a linear increase expressed by the equation: $Y = 0.00010292X$, with a coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.629$. This indicates that nearly two-thirds of the variation in natural biodiversity is explained by the distance to the urban center, suggesting a clear positive relationship. That is, the further the plots are from the central urbanization, the higher the

proportion of native species relative to introduced ones. It is observed that beyond 8,000 m, in semi-rural transition zones, natural biodiversity is high and tends toward 0.8 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Regression of Natural Biodiversity (BN') and distance to the urban center (DC).

The regression analysis between natural biodiversity (BN') and the natural area likewise shows a linear relationship expressed by: $Y = 0.526X$, with a coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.242$, suggesting that approximately one-quarter of the observed natural biodiversity can be explained by the available natural area. For example, when the built-up area within a 100 m radius reaches 50% (0.5), natural biodiversity drops to 0.263; that is, it is reduced to a quarter of its potential natural value (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Regression analysis between Natural Biodiversity (BN') and natural area (NA).

4. Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate a clear relationship between urbanization and woody flora biodiversity. There is a general trend of biodiversity increasing as sampling plots move further away from the urban center, confirming the negative impact of urbanization on native flora in the innermost zones. However, this trend is not entirely uniform, as urbanization does not follow a perfectly concentric pattern. It was observed that vegetation patches can persist in areas closer to the center, whereas urban corridors can extend across considerable distances, fragmenting peri-urban habitats.

Furthermore, the coefficient of determination between the distance to the urban center and the natural area is $R^2 = 0.451$. Although a stronger relationship between distance and natural area might be expected, this value indicates that less than 50% of the variation in natural area is explained by distance to the center. These findings are consistent with recent studies exploring the relationship between urbanization and plant diversity. Hou et al. (2023), in a global meta-analysis on plants, documented that urbanization exerts negative effects on native species and positive or neutral effects on introduced species. This pattern aligns with the findings of this research: native species predominate further from the urban center, where urbanization pressure is lower.

Additionally, Cao et al. (2024) found that trees, shrubs, and herbaceous species respond differently to urban drivers such as night lighting, road density, and Point of Interest (POI) density. In particular, herbaceous species are more sensitive to urbanization than trees, which may explain why the regressions utilizing natural area exhibit a moderate explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.242$).

A critical finding of this study is that the impact on local biodiversity does not depend exclusively on the quantitative species richness of exotic flora (64 species compared to 62 native species), but rather on the functional nature and ecological behavior of these introductions. To accurately interpret the dynamics of the urban-rural gradient in this binational border, it is imperative to establish a taxonomic and ecological distinction between exotic species of an "anthropophilic or soft" nature and those possessing true transformative invasive potential.

Richardson et al. (2000) formalized the conceptual framework that dissociates these ecological behaviors. According to these authors, introduced or exotic species are those that overcome biogeographical barriers due to direct or indirect human intervention, but whose persistence in the new environment is typically restricted to intensely modified habitats or under constant management. In our research, this group is clearly represented by urban fruit trees and strict ornamentals, such as *Citrus sinensis* or *Camellia japonica*. These species exert spatial pressure within the innermost strata (Strata I and II) but display scarce or null autonomous dispersal and recruitment capacity within disturbed forest patches, behaving as passive components of the urban landscape.

Conversely, Richardson et al. (2000) define invasive species as a subcategory of naturalized plants that produce viable offspring at considerable distances from the original introduction sites, possessing the potential to transform the structure and function of native ecosystems. The census data across this gradient alarmingly reflect this behavior in taxa such as *Ligustrum lucidum*, the genus *Eucalyptus* (with a notable dominance of 173 individuals), and the genus *Pinus* (with 39 recorded individuals, led by *Pinus elliottii*).

While urban fruit trees remain confined by biotic and anthropogenic barriers, *Ligustrum lucidum* and forest escapes of *Eucalyptus* and *Pinus* act as transformer species. In the specific

case of Pinaceae, their invasion success in the region is widely documented due to their massive production of seeds adapted for anemochorous (wind) dispersal and their capacity to modify the physicochemical conditions of the soil, which inhibits the germination of the surrounding native flora (Zenni & Simberloff, 2013). These exotic woody species exploit landscape fragmentation and the availability of open areas to actively colonize ecotones and native forest edges as distance from the center increases (Strata III to V), competing directly with the local flora.

Therefore, the general classification of "introduced" used in the quantitative data matrix must be qualitatively nuanced for transboundary territorial management: the actual ecological pressure on the biodiversity of the Pampean-subtropical native forest does not stem from the overall diversity of exotic species present within the urban fabric, but rather from the colonization of peri-urban patches by those few high-biomass species (*Eucalyptus*, *Pinus*, *Ligustrum*) equipped with invasive functional traits that rupture the local biotic barrier. The multiple linear regression model was constructed to predict the Natural Biodiversity Index (BN') as a function of the Distance to the Center (DC) and the Construction-Free Area Ratio (C). The resulting model was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) and is expressed by the following predictive (equation 2):

$$NB' = 0.2917 + 4.91 \cdot DC + 0.3707 \cdot C \quad (2)$$

The adjusted coefficient of determination ($R^2_{adj.} = 0.355$) indicates that 35.5% of the variability in natural biodiversity is jointly explained by the distance to the urban center and the construction-free area ratio. Both predictors proved to be individually significant (DC : $p < 0.001$; C : $p = 0.001$). The effect of the Construction-Free Area Ratio (C), which represents the local proportion of natural area, is the most powerful: a 10-percentage-point increase in the free area (a 0.1 increase in the ratio) is associated with a 0.037-point increase in BN' , holding distance constant. Although C alone explained only a quarter of the variability ($R^2 = 0.242$), its significance within the multiple model demonstrates that local habitat quality is a key and independent predictor once the Distance to the Center (DC) is controlled. This result, albeit more modest in its adjusted R^2 compared to the strong simple linear relationship (DC vs. NB' , $R^2 = 0.629$), is ecologically more compelling as it validates both spatial scales.

Simkin et al. (2022) projected that global urban expansion threatens the biodiversity of more than 30,000 vertebrate species by 2050, showing that city growth is a major driver of habitat loss and fragmentation. Their findings support the idea that urban areas encroach upon natural habitats and that distance to the urban center can serve as a reliable proxy for the degree of disturbance.

In line with these findings, Aronson et al. (2014) analyzed 110 cities worldwide and concluded that, while cities can harbor considerable plant diversity, it is dominated by introduced species, which reduces the ecological functionality of urban ecosystems. This reinforces the observation that fragments closer to the urban center tend to lose functional connectivity with larger natural areas. From the above, two major points can be inferred. First, although many cities grow in an approximately radial fashion, this expansion is neither perfectly circular nor homogeneous. As pointed out by Cao et al. (2024), the local distribution of infrastructure, roads, or human activity can generate irregular fragmentation and alter the relationship between distance and natural cover. Second, relatively construction-free fragments near the urban center may have lost functional connectivity with larger natural areas, which

favors the predominance of introduced or planted species. This ecological isolation phenomenon is consistent with the implications of urban sprawl discussed by Simkin et al. (2022), who warn that urban expansion not only consumes land but also fragments and isolates habitats.

In this regard, McKinney (2006) argues that urbanization creates ecological filters that favor disturbance-tolerant species, which explains the dominance of exotic species in dense urban zones. This perspective complements the findings of the present study regarding the loss of native biodiversity in innermost areas. Additionally, the comparative analysis between both sides of the border revealed a significant difference in landscaping policies. Urban forestry on the Brazilian side exhibited a higher proportion of native species compared to the Uruguayan side. This finding suggests the existence of distinct urban landscape management strategies in both cities. On the other hand, the influence of land-use policies on floristic composition was identified. In the peri-urban areas of Rivera, a high abundance of individuals belonging to the genus *Eucalyptus* was recorded, a fact directly associated with national afforestation policies implemented in the Department of Rivera. Notably, one of the sampled plots on the Brazilian side, which by chance happened to be located within the Ibirapuitã Environmental Protection Area (*Reserva Biológica de Ibirapuitã*), did not present any exotic species, underscoring the vital importance of conservation areas in preserving native flora against urbanization pressure.

5. Conclusions

Urbanization reduces native biodiversity: It was verified that natural biodiversity increases with distance from the urban center, clearly demonstrating the negative impact of urbanization on indigenous woody flora. **The scale effect of green spaces:** Although the presence of green spaces promotes biodiversity, its effect is less determinant than the distance to the urban core. This highlights the crucial importance of integrating multiple spatial factors into territorial planning.

Asymmetry of urban growth: Urbanization is neither uniform nor symmetrical; rather, urban growth exhibits irregular patterns that drive habitat fragmentation. This dynamics allows vegetation patches to persist within central areas while simultaneously enabling urban sprawl to encroach upon peripheral zones characterized by high floristic richness.

Predominance of exotic species: Exotic species predominate in heavily urbanized zones. The most disturbed sectors recorded a higher proportion of introduced species, whereas native species predominated in more distant or less intervened areas. **Loss of ecological connectivity facilitates invasion:** Isolated vegetation fragments near the urban center have lost functional connectivity with larger natural ecosystems. This ecological isolation facilitates the establishment of exotic species and significantly reduces overall ecosystem resilience.

Impact of urban management policies: Urban policies directly shape plant diversity. The observed differences between the two border cities regarding the proportion of native species in urban forestry reflect the immediate impact of localized landscape management decisions. **The essential role of protected areas:** Conservation areas are vital for biodiversity preservation. Zones under environmental protection exhibited higher ecological integrity and a lower presence of exotic species, underscoring their strategic value for safeguarding regional native flora. **Integration of conservation into land-use planning:** The protection of native forests cannot be achieved in isolation; it requires a comprehensive territorial vision that effectively combines *in situ* conservation, ecological connectivity, and sustainable design criteria across both urban and rural landscapes.

References

- Alonso Paz, E., & Bassagoda, M. J. (2002). *La vegetación costera del SE uruguayo: ambientes y biodiversidad*. *Ciência & Ambiente*, 24, 35–48.
- Araujo, A. C. B., Gracioli, C. R., Grimm, E. L., & Longhi, S. J. (2012). The assessment of floristic composition, size, health and current tree conservation of the International Park in Sant’Ana do Livramento, Brazil and Rivera, Uruguay. *REVSBAU*, 7(1), 66–74.
- Aronson, M. F. J., Handel, S. N., La Puma, I. P., & Clemants, S. E. (2014). Changes in plant diversity along an urban–rural gradient in an agricultural landscape. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 132, 10–21.
- Bennadji, Z., Ferreira, F., Castillo, D., & Alfonso, M. (2014). Development of strategies for the valorization of native tree flora in Uruguay: From bioprospecting to biorefinery. *Revista INIA*, (39), 57–61.
- Bowler, D. E., Bjorkman, A. D., & Hines, J. (2022). Positive effects of species dampened by neighborhood heterogeneity. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 31(8), 1609–1621.
- Capdevila-Argüelles, L., Zilletti, B., & Suárez Álvarez, V. A. (2005). Causas de la pérdida de biodiversidad: Especies exóticas invasoras. *Ambienta*, (47), 19–24.
- Cárdenas, E., & Vásquez, G. (2021). How to bloom the green desert: Eucalyptus plantations and native forests in Uruguay beyond black and white perspectives. *Forests*, 9(10), 614.
- Cao, L., Wang, G., Yang, F., He, R., & Zhao, Y. (2024). Urbanization and plant diversity in urban fringes: Differential responses across life forms. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 371, 123151.
- Díaz, R. Y., Niell, S., Cesio, M. V., & Heinzen, H. (2021). Floral food resources for *Apis mellifera* in a protected area of native forest in Uruguay. *Agrociencia Uruguay*, 25(2), e426.
- Fernandez, R. D., et al. (2020). A global review of *Ligustrum lucidum* (Oleaceae) invasion. *Botanical Review*, 86(2), 93–118.
- García, D., Cabaña, T., & Perdomo, L. (2024). Disentangling the invasion process of subtropical native forests of Uruguay by the exotic tree *Ligustrum lucidum*. *Ecological Processes*, 13, Article 17.
- Haretche, F., Mai, P., & Brazeiro, A. (2012). Woody flora of Uruguay: Inventory and implication within the Pampean region. *Acta Botanica Brasilica*, 26(3), 537–552.
- Heywood, V. H., & Iriondo, J. M. (2003). Conservation of plant biodiversity: Current status and future prospects. *Biological Conservation*, 113(3), 383–393.
- Hou, Y., Li, J., Li, G., Qi, W., & colaboradores. (2023). Negative effects of urbanization on plants: A global meta-analysis. *Ecology and Evolution*, 13, e9894.
- Kaul, A. D., & Wilsey, B. J. (2021). Exotic species drive patterns of plant species diversity in 93 restored tallgrass prairies. *Ecological Applications*, 31(2), e02274.
- Traversa, I., Nolla, S., & Mallo, A. [2026]. Plant biodiversity in the urban-rural gradient of the Uruguay-Brazil binational border. v2. 13 p. Zenodo. [10.5281/zenodo.20401780].

Martínez-Dueñas, W. A. (2010). INRA - Índice Integrado Relativo de Antropización: Propuesta técnico-conceptual y aplicación. *Revista Intropica*, 5(1), 45–54.

McKinney, M. L. (2006). Efectos de la urbanización en la riqueza de especies: Una revisión de plantas y animales. *Ecosyst Urbano*, 11, 161–176.

Pacheco Cobeña, A. J., & Guerrero Calero, J. M. (2024). Estudio comparativo de la biodiversidad en ecosistemas urbanos y rurales del cantón Portoviejo, Manabí, Ecuador. *Código Científico Revista de Investigación*, 5(2), 18–34.

Peng, S., Kinlock, N. L., Gurevitch, J., & Peng, S. (2019). Correlation of native and exotic species richness: A global meta-analysis finds no invasion paradox across scales. *Ecology*, 100(1), e02552.

Resende Araújo, M., Silva, R. R., Santos, F. M., & Ferreira, J. A. (2022). Comportamento fenológico das espécies *Jacaranda mimosifolia* e *Ligustrum lucidum* na arborização urbana. *Nativa*, 10(1), 74–82.

Richardson, D. M., Pyšek, P., Rejmánek, M., Barbour, M. G., Panetta, F. D., & West, C. J. (2000). Naturalization and invasion of alien plants: concepts and definitions. *Diversity and Distributions*, 6(2), 93–107. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1472-4642.2000.00083.x>

Rossignaud, J., Carboni, M., & Münkemüller, T. (2022). Effects of competition and habitat heterogeneity on native–exotic plant richness relationships across spatial scales. *Diversity and Distributions*, 28(9), 1432–1445.

Sanz-Elorza, M., Dana, E. D., & Sobrino, E. (2018). Las invasiones biológicas en España: Una visión global de sus impactos. *Ecosistemas*, 27(1), 1–13.

Seto, K. C., Güneralp, B., & Hutyra, L. R. (2012). Global forecasts of urban expansion to 2030 and direct impacts on biodiversity and carbon pools. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(40), 16083–16088.

Simkin, R. D., Seto, K. C., McDonald, R. I., & Jetz, W. (2022). Biodiversity impacts and conservation implications of urban land expansion projected by 2050. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(12), e2117297119.

Traversa, I. (2024). New biodiversity index for anthropized and natural areas. *Balduinia*, (73), 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.5902/2358198089232>

Traversa, I. P., & Alejano-Monge, M. R. (2013). Caracterización, distribución y manejo de los bosques nativos en el norte de Uruguay. *Revista Mexicana de Biodiversidad*, 84(1), 249–262. <https://doi.org/10.7550/rmb.23314>

Vakhlamova, T., Rusterholz, H. P., Kanayev, A., & Baur, B. (2014). Changes in plant diversity along an urban–rural gradient in an expanding city in Kazakhstan, Western Siberia. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 132, 111–120.

Zenni, R. D., & Simberloff, D. (2013). Number of introduction events, time since introduction, and biological traits explain the status of foreign species in Germany and species invasiveness in United States and Brazil. *Biological Invasions*, 15(8), 1775–1791. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-012-0408-z>

Traversa, I., Nolla, S., & Mallo, A. [2026]. Plant biodiversity in the urban-rural gradient of the Uruguay-Brazil binational border. v2. 13 p. Zenodo. [10.5281/zenodo.20401780].